

Innovative concepts and technologies for ecologically sustainable nutrient management in agriculture aiming to prevent, mitigate and eliminate pollution in soils, water, and air

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PRACTICE ABSTRACT BATCH 1

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EXECUTIVE SUMMARY

The ECONUTRI project is commissioned to scientifically support the EU’s Green Deal in its target to reduce by 50% the losses of nutrients originating from organic biomass and crop fertilisation, thereby reducing the fertiliser use by at least 20% by 2030. To address this objective, ECONUTRI deploys 24 innovative technologies (Table 1), with a sound potential to reduce nutrient emissions in agriculture. Most of these innovative technologies are nature-based solutions (NbS) originating from previous research work with a TRL of 4-6. The objective of ECONUTRI is to optimise, validate, and demonstrate these 24 technologies in operational environment, thus increasing their TRL to 7-9. These technologies are integrated parts of a holistic concept based on recycling of nutrients and organic material, novel machinery and fertilisers, novel decision support systems (DSS), and novel nutrient management plans incorporating nature-based solutions to reduce nutrient losses and to increase nutrient use efficiency. The ultimate objective of ECONUTRI is to contribute to the adoption of these 24 innovative technologies at large scale in agriculture. As a contribution to this objective, a practice abstract (PA) has been compiled for 15 out of the 24 innovative technologies providing concise information about their practical application. The criterion to select the 15 out of the 24 innovative technologies was the level of their ripeness for commercial application. Practice abstracts for the 9 technologies for which no practice abstract is included in the current Deliverable, will be presented in the second batch of PAs, particularly in D7.3. Most practice abstracts are allocated into the subheadings: background knowledge (stating the problem to be addressed), the suggested ECONUTRI solution, the limitations in their commercial application, and outlook. Four practice abstracts originate from innovative technologies allocated to WP2, six of them originate from WP3, and finally, five PAs arise from innovations included in WP4. A full list of the 15 PAs originating from 15 innovative technologies of ECONUTRI is provided in Table 2.

D7.2 was not included in the ECONUTRI proposal but was suggested to the consortium by the Project Officer (PO) for inclusion in WP7 during the preparation of the GA. Therefore, D7.1 is not referenced in any specific task in the Grant Agreement. However, D7.2 is part of Task 7.1, as one of the coordinator’s subtasks in Task 7.1 is to “coordinate scientific and administrative activities”. Indeed, one of the scientific activities coordinated by AUA was the presentation in a simple form of 15 out of the 24 technologies deployed by ECONUTRI as practice abstracts (PAs). The PAs describe concisely 15 technologies commissioned to contribute to reduction of nutrient pollution in a style that can be understandable by non-experts and especially by growers and other professionals in the agri-food chain.

Table 1. The 24 innovative technologies deployed by ECONUTRI to minimise pollution of water resources and air by nutrient emissions originating from agriculture.

No	Short description of the technology	WP	Current TRL	Expected TRL
1	Technologies to utilize animal manure and slurry as fertilisers	2	6	8
2.	Technologies for nutrient recovery and safe land application of raw waste materials	2	5-6	8
3.	Technologies for optimization of composting using novel microbial consortia	2	4	7
4.	Technologies for nutrient calibration of materials derived from biowaste processing	2	5	7- 8
5.	Technologies to optimize field application of materials derived from biowaste processing	2	4-6	8
6.	Circular systems for biowaste utilisation in greenhouses	2	4-5	8
7.	Circular systems for biowaste utilisation in open field	2	4-5	7- 8
8.	Precision fertilization in field crops using sensing technologies	3	5	7
9.	Novel intercropping technologies to maximize N ₂ input in organic cropping	3	5	7- 8
10.	Integrating organic with mineral fertilisation to maximise P input from organic sources	3	5	7
11.	Crop-demand driven nutrient management in conventional vegetable crops using DSSs	3	5-6	8
12.	Integrated nutrient management by DSSs and alternate irrigation to minimise nutrient losses in organic cropping	3	5	8
13.	Real-time sensing with ISEs to maximise nutrient recycling in soilless cropping	3	5	8-9
14.	Cascade soilless system to reuse the effluents in a sequence of crops	3	5	7
15.	Novel biostimulants based on strigolactones and small RNAs to improve NUE	3	4-5	7
16.	Improving NUE by innovative fertilisers and additives	3	5-6	7-8
17.	Reducing GHG and NH ₃ emissions from barns through additives	4	4	7
18.	Reducing GHG and NH ₃ emissions from barns through management adaptations	4	5	8
19.	Reducing GHG and NH ₃ emissions during storage of organic residues through additives	4	6	8
20.	Reducing GHG and NH ₃ emissions from biowaste through management adaptations	4	5	7, 8
21.	Reducing GHG emissions from soil grown crops through additives to fertilizers	4	4	7, 8
22.	Reducing GHG emissions through organic farming practices	4	4	7
23.	Reducing GHG and NH ₃ emissions by optimising field application of manure/slurry	4	6	8
24.	Reducing GHG and NH ₃ emissions through measurement feedback	4	5	8

Table 2. Titles of the 15 practice abstracts included in this deliverable, Work Package (WP) they originate and lead author.

	Title	WP	Main author	Partner
1	Performing variable rate application of manure for fertilisation	WP2	Thanasis Tzimourtas	AUA
2	Nutrient recovery from liquid waste materials through microbial immobilization in compost	WP2	Damianos Neocleous	ARI
3	FarmMaps side dressing APP includes N-mineralisation from organic amendments to improve N-use efficiency	WP2	Annette Pronk	WUR
4	Recycling of vegetable wastes by ultra-high temperature aerobic composting	WP2	Ruixue Chang	CAU
5	Integrated cropping to minimise fertiliser reliance in low-input legume-based rotations.	WP3	Cathy Hawes	JHI
6	Variable rate application manure taskmaps	WP3	Koen Uyttenhove	ODYC
7	Using VegSyst-DSS to prepare irrigation and N plans for fertigated vegetable crops grown in greenhouses	WP3	Rodney Thompson	UAL
8	Smart irrigation management to optimize the nutrient use efficiency in organic tomato crops	WP3	Ioannis Karavidas	AUA
9	Recycling the fertigation effluents in closed-loop soilless crops using ion selective electrodes and the decision support system NUTRISENSE	WP3	Dimitrios Savvas	AUA
10	Cascade hydroponics can increase water and nutrients use efficiency of greenhouse production systems	WP3	Nikolaos Katsoulas	UTH
11	The use of urease inhibitors to reduce ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions from dairy barns	WP4	Wajid Umar	ATB
12	Reducing GHG and NH3 emissions from barns and during storage of organic residues through biochar	WP4	Dionysis Sparaggis	ARI
13	Reducing GHG emissions from horticultural crops using biofertilizer enriched with beneficial microorganisms	WP4	Sas-Paszt Lidia	INHORT
14	Reduction of GHG emissions with optimised machinery	WP4	Jelle Vervaet	VERVAET
15	The use of an emission monitoring system to reduce the ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions from barns	WP4	Chari Vandenbussche	EV ILVO

LIST OF PRACTICE ABSTRACTS

1 PERFORMING VARIABLE RATE APPLICATION OF MANURE FOR FERTILISATION

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KEYWORDS: variable rate application, fertilizer, manure, slurry, precision

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): Performing variable rate application of manure for fertilisation

Background

When chemical fertilisers are excessively used, they contaminate water and cause nutrients to be lost via runoff. Traditional manure causes an imbalance in the nutrients in the soil and water, which makes these problems even more severe. Utilising innovative methods is essential in order to maximise the efficiency with which nutrients are applied and to lessen the influence that they have on the surrounding ecosystem.

The EcoNutri Solution

The robust EcoNutri controller, which is a raspberry pi 4, uses the Global Navigation Satellite System (GNSS) to accurately regulate fertiliser delivery and device location. Recipe maps alter a three-way valve's opening to enhance the supply of nutrients. The variable rate approach increases crop output while minimising environmental effect by optimising fertiliser application. Accurately measuring manure with modern flowmeters improves recipe mapping. So, the aforesaid technology uses an intelligent mechanism to achieve a variable fertiliser dosage.

Limitations

Although the EcoNutri technology for variable rate application of manure provides a number of benefits, it also has some drawbacks. The proposed method has a disadvantage in that it just requires one tube that is installed on the ground to provide fertiliser [1].

Outlook

EcoNutri, use precision agricultural technology, is in accordance with increasingly stringent environmental standards. Advancing technology has the potential for improved efficiency to achieve maximum effectiveness [2].

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN NATIVE LANGUAGE): Πραγματοποιώντας εφαρμογή

μεταβλητής δόσης ζωικής κοπριάς για λίπανση

Υπόβαθρο

Όταν τα χημικά λιπάσματα χρησιμοποιούνται υπερβολικά, μολύνουν το νερό και προκαλούν απώλεια θρεπτικών συστατικών μέσω της απορροής. Η χρήση καινοτόμων μεθόδων είναι απαραίτητη προκειμένου να μεγιστοποιηθεί η αποτελεσματικότητα με την οποία εφαρμόζονται τα θρεπτικά συστατικά και να μειωθεί η επιρροή που έχουν στο περιβάλλον οικοσύστημα.

Η λύση EcoNutri

Το ECONUTRI αναπτύσσει έναν έξυπνο ελεγκτή που χρησιμοποιεί το Παγκόσμιο Σύστημα Δορυφόρου Πλοήγησης (GNSS) για να διαχειρίζεται με ακρίβεια την εφαρμογή κοπριάς και την τοποθέτηση της συσκευής. Οι χάρτες συνταγών αλλάζουν το άνοιγμα μιας βαλβίδας τριών κατευθύνσεων για να αυξήσουν την παροχή θρεπτικών συστατικών. Η προσέγγιση μεταβλητού ποσοστού βελτιστοποιεί την προσφορά λιπασμάτων, αυξάνοντας την παραγωγή καλλιεργειών και μειώνοντας τις περιβαλλοντικές επιπτώσεις. Το ψηφιακό ροόμετρο ενισχύουν τους χάρτες συνταγών μετρώντας με ακρίβεια την κοπριά.

Περιορισμοί

Αν και η συγκεκριμένη τεχνολογία παρέχει μια σειρά από πλεονεκτήματα, έχει επίσης κάποια μειονεκτήματα. Η προτεινόμενη μέθοδος έχει ένα βασικό μειονέκτημα στο ότι χρησιμοποιεί απλώς έναν σωλήνα που είναι εγκατεστημένος στο έδαφος για την παροχή λιπάσματος [1].

Σύνοψη

Η μεταβλητή δόση ζωικής κοπριάς για λίπανση είναι μια γεωργική τεχνολογία ακριβείας, η οποία είναι σύμφωνη με ολοένα και πιο αυστηρά περιβαλλοντικά πρότυπα. Η προηγμένη τεχνολογία έχει τη δυνατότητα για βελτιωμένη απόδοση, όταν συνδυάζεται με βιώσιμες πρακτικές, για την επίτευξη της μέγιστης αποτελεσματικότητας [2].

Bibliographic References

1. S. J. D. A. M. S. B. X. P. Suvendran, "Effect of Irrigation Water Quality and Soil Compost Treatment on Salinity Management to Improve Soil Health and Plant Yield," *Water (Switzerland)*, vol. 16, no. 10, pp. 1-19, 2024.
2. S. Teten, "University of Nebraska-Lincoln," 26 4 2021. [Online]. Available: <https://water.unl.edu/article/animal-manure-management/variable-rate-manure-applications-based-upon-management-zones>

2 NUTRIENT RECOVERY FROM LIQUID WASTE MATERIALS THROUGH MICROBIAL IMMOBILIZATION IN COMPOST

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KEYWORDS: co-composting, green waste, nutrient-rich liquid waste materials

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): Nutrient recovery from liquid waste materials through microbial immobilization in compost.

Background

Digestate from biogas production plants and drain-to-waste hydroponic solutions constitute liquid wastes rich in nutrients like N and P, the majority of which is lost during storage or disposal. In parallel, dry green waste remains unexploited due to its high C:N ratio.

The ECONUTRI solution

The innovation here refers to the reduction of vulnerability to loss of nutrients (especially N and P) contained in digestate or hydroponic waste solution through immobilization in microbial biomass, which develops during composting [1]. A secondary aim is the exploitation of green waste and particularly this that has dried and is difficult to compost directly.

Description of the suggested technology

Co-composting green waste with digestate or hydroponic waste. Mixing a rich in N solution with tree plant residues may serve as a way of stabilizing N and restricting NH₃ losses [1]. Trials indicated that stabilization was due to initial immobilization in microbial biomass or dead microbial biomass, leading to stronger N fixation in organic compounds or later attachment of inorganic N to the organic residue matrix.

Limitations

Optimization and further actions to convince producers of the potential benefits of co-composting.

Outlook

The ideal application of the technology would be to extend the activities of biogas plants to include composting units very close to the digestate storage/drying lagoons. The transfer of municipal green waste to the premises of biogas plants it could significantly facilitate the appropriate mixing of digestate with shredded woody material.

ABSTRACT TITLE (NATIVE LANGUAGE): Ανάκτηση θρεπτικών ουσιών από υγρά απόβλητα υλικά μέσω μικροβιακής ακινητοποίησης στο κόμποστ

Εισαγωγή

Το χωνεμένο υλικό (χώνευμα/digestate) από μονάδες παραγωγής βιοαερίου και τα υδροπονικά θρεπτικά διαλύματα περιέχουν μεγάλες ποσότητες θρεπτικών συστατικών όπως N και P, μεγάλο μέρος των οποίων χάνεται κατά την αποθήκευση ή την απόρριψή τους. Ταυτόχρονα, τα ξηρά πράσινα απορρίματα παραμένουν ανεκμετάλλευτα λόγω της υψηλής αναλογίας C:N, η οποία δεν επιτρέπει την κομποστοποίηση και τη χρήση τους στη γεωργία.

Η λύση που προτείνει το ECONUTRI

Η καινοτομία αναφέρεται (α) στη μείωση της απώλειας θρεπτικών ουσιών (ιδιαίτερα N και P) που περιέχονται στο χωνεμένο υπόλειμμα ή τα υδροπονικά απόβλητα μέσω της ακινητοποίησης στη μικροβιακή βιομάζα, η οποία αναπτύσσεται κατά την κομποστοποίηση [1] και (β) στην εκμετάλλευση των πράσινων απορριμμάτων (κλαδέματα) και ιδιαίτερα αυτών που έχουν αποξηραθεί και είναι δύσκολο να κομποστοποιηθούν.

Περιγραφή προτεινόμενης τεχνολογίας

Η συν-κομποστοποίηση πράσινων απορριμμάτων με χωνεμένα ή υδροπονικά απόβλητα μπορεί να επιτευχθεί σε δύο στάδια [1]. Πρώτον, η ανάμειξη των δύο υλικών σε μια δεξαμενή για να έρθουν σε επαφή και να μουλιάσουν και ακολούθως τη δημιουργία σωρού κομπόστας όπου οι διαδικασίες μικροβιακής αποσύνθεσης θα ακινητοποιήσουν τα θρεπτικά συστατικά μετατρέποντάς τα σε μια πιο σταθερή οργανική μορφή.

Περιορισμοί

Βελτιστοποίηση και περαιτέρω ενέργειες χρειάζονται για να πειστούν οι παραγωγοί για τα πιθανά οφέλη της συν-κομποστοποίησης.

Προοπτική

Η επέκταση των δραστηριοτήτων των μονάδων βιοαερίου ώστε να συμπεριλάβουν μονάδες συν-κομποστοποίησης. Η μεταφορά των αστικών πράσινων αποβλήτων στις εγκαταστάσεις των μονάδων βιοαερίου θα μπορούσε να διευκολύνει σημαντικά την κατάλληλη ανάμειξη του χωνεύματος με το τεμαχισμένο ξυλώδες υλικό.

Bibliographic references

1. Franke-Whittle, I.H., Confalonieri, A., Insam, H., Schlegelmilch, M. and Körner, I., 2014. Changes in the microbial communities during co-composting of digestates. *Waste Management*, 34(3), pp.632-641.

3 FARM MAPS SIDE DRESSING APP INCLUDES N-MINERALISATION FROM ORGANIC AMENDMENTS TO IMPROVE N-USE EFFICIENCY

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KEYWORDS: organic amendments/fertilisers & nutrient release, farmmaps side dressing app

ABSTRACT TITLE: FarmMaps side dressing APP includes N-mineralisation from organic amendments to improve N-use efficiency

Background

Frequently use of organic amendments increases nitrogen release with subsequent risks of overfertilization, losses to the environment, and low N use efficiencies. N release from organic amendments is hardly included in N-fertilizer strategies.

The ECONUTRI solution

The digital platform FarmMaps helps farmers with management decisions [1] of which side dressing, a well-known strategy to improve N use efficiency is one. Organic amendments contribute to the N supply by mineralisation. ECONUTRI supports improved decision making on N side dressing as organic amendments N release is included.

Description of the suggested technology

FarmMaps offers a side dressing advice based on a variety of techniques (<https://www.farmmaps.net/en/>). None of these techniques include N release from organic amendments. Within ECONUTRI, N release is estimated through a modelling approach including weather and soil data, organic amendment characteristics and dose [2]. Innovative products and standard products are included in the on-line side dressing APP. Farmers can compare the APP with and without N release, to modify their N side dressing, increase N-use efficiency and reduce environmental impacts without yield losses.

Limitations

FarmMaps uses general data through GPS locations of farmers' fields, which may deviate from actual data but allows users to include site specific soil data to tune N release to their location.

Outlook

Organic amendments are screened for N-mineralization characteristics, validated and included into the APP. FarmMaps is upgraded to include world-wide access.

ABSTRACT TITLE: FarmMaps bijbemestings APP houdt rekening met N-mineralisatie uit organische producten.

Achtergrond

VHet veelvuldig gebruik van organische producten verhoogt de N-mineralisatie. Hierdoor neemt het risico op overbemesting en verliezen voor naar het milieu toe enterwijl de N-efficiëntie afneemt. N-mineralisatie uit organische producten wordt nauwelijks meegenomen in N-bemestingsstrategieën.

De ECONUTRI oplossing

Het digitale platform FarmMaps helpt boeren bij managementbeslissingen [1]. N-bijbemesting is een bekende methode om de N-efficiëntie te verbeteren. Organische producten dragen via mineralisatie bij aan de N-voorziening. ECONUTRI ondersteunt een verbeterde N-bijbemesting door rekening te houden met N-mineralisatie uit de organische producten.

Beschrijving van de voorgestelde oplossing

Verschillende technieken zijn beschikbaar in FarmMaps voor de berkening van de N bijbemesting wordt berekent (<https://www.farmmaps.net/en/>). Geen van deze technieken houdt rekening met mineralisatie van N uit organische producten. In ECONUTRI berekent een model de N-mineralisatie met weer- en bodemgegevens, organische product eigenschappen en dosering [2]. Innovatieve en standaardproducten zijn opgenomen in de online N-bijbemestings-APP. Boeren kunnen de APP vergelijken met en zonder de aanover van organische producten.

Beperkingen

FarmMaps gebruikt GPS-locaties voor algemene gegevens gebaseerd op de GPS-locaties, en die kunnen afwijken van de werkelijke gegevens. maar gGebruik van eigen bodemgegevens is mogelijk.

Vooruitblik

De N mineralisatie van organische producten wordt bepaald, gevalideerd en opgenomen in de APP. FarmMaps wordt geüpgraded tot wereldwijde toegang.

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4 RECYCLING OF VEGETABLE WASTES BY ULTRA-HIGH TEMPERATURE AEROBIC COMPOSTING

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KEYWORDS: composting, nutrient recycling, organic fertiliser

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): Recycling of vegetable wastes by ultra-high temperature aerobic composting

Background

There are many vegetable wastes (VM) produced every year all over the world, which contained nutrients for plants while pathogens harmful for soil and plants. Due to the dual attributes of VM, composting is a useful treating technology because of the thermophilic stage, while the nitrogen loss and ammonia emission would be higher in this stage.

The ECONUTRI solution

An environment-friendly ultra-high temperature composting technology was developed. It can achieve 100% elimination of pathogenic microorganisms by maintaining the temperature above 70°C, speed up the composting process and shorten the duration to 10-15 days by accelerating material degradation, and reduce the greenhouse gases and nutrient loss by 30% [1, 2, 3]). Functional vegetable seedling/cultivation substrate was developed from the compost product instead of grass carbon consumption by up to 80%, whose product also had the function of antagonizing root-node nematodes and some soil-borne diseases [4].

Limitations

The application of the technology needs the basic information of the materials, both the main material and auxiliary materials, meanwhile the process management is also for the thermophilic stage control.

Outlook

The technology can be applied in vegetable parks for in situ treatment and utilization. Farmers mix vegetable waste with surrounding straws to realize ultra-high temperature composting by setting the bulk density, organic matter composition and moisture content of the material, which can reduce the cost and risk of collection, transportation and treatment of wastes, as well as the subsequent use of fertilizers and pesticides, and reduce the cost input of farmers.

ABSTRACT TITLE (NATIVE LANGUAGE): 处理蔬菜废弃物的超高温好氧堆肥技术

研究背景

世界各地每年产生大量的蔬菜废弃物，其中含有对植物有益的营养物质，同时又含有对土壤和植物有害的病原体。基于蔬菜废弃物的双重属性，具有高温阶段的好氧堆肥是一种安全有用的处理技术，但高温阶段会增加堆肥处理的氮损失和氨排放。

ECONUTRI解决方案

项目单位开发了一种环境友好型的超高温堆肥技术。通过保持温度在70°C以上，可以100%消除病原微生物；通过加速材料降解，可将堆肥时间缩短至10-15天，减少30%的温室气体和养分损失[1, 2, 3]。基于超高温堆肥产物制备的功能性蔬菜苗木/栽培基质可最高替代草炭80%，同时具有拮抗根节线虫和一些土传疾病的功能[4]。

应用限制

该技术的应用需要材料的基本信息，包括主要材料和辅助材料，同时对好氧堆肥的高温阶段进行严格管理。

推广前景

该技术可用于蔬菜园区废弃物的原位处理和利用。农民通过设定物料的容重、有机质组成和含水率，将蔬菜废弃物与秸秆等其他废弃物共同开展超高温堆肥，可以降低废弃物的收集、运输、处理以及后续化肥、农药的使用成本和风险，降低农民的成本投入。

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5 INTEGRATED CROPPING TO MINIMISE FERTILISER RELIANCE IN LOW-INPUT LEGUME-BASED ROTATIONS

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KEYWORDS: regenerative agriculture, integrated cropping, biodiversity, soil health

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): Integrated cropping to minimise fertiliser reliance in low-input legume-based rotations

Background

High crop productivity can be achieved with less mineral fertilisers by integrating soil and crop management options for multiple benefits to soil health and biodiversity [1]. Integrated management options improve resource utilisation efficiency and reduce avoidable losses of nutrients from the cropped area.

The ECONUTRI solution

A legume-based, low-input crop system improves sustainability by increasing resource use efficiency, utilizing legumes as an alternative nitrogen source, and reducing nutrient losses. Together, these interventions produce less pollution, enhance biodiversity, improve soil health, and yield comparable to conventionally managed crops [2].

The suggested technology

The integrated system combines occasional tillage (plough one year in six), organic matter amendments (ca. 10 t ha⁻¹ yr⁻¹ green waste compost, crop residues, cover crops) in a legume-based rotation with 15% cropped and 50% undersown legumes for Biological N Fixation and Soil Nitrogen Supply. This system cuts mineral fertilizer requirements by 40-60% with further reductions likely long-term.

Limitations

Although the long-term benefits are clear, combining the full range of interventions may not always be practical. The choice of management options must be tailored to each circumstance and flexibility in development and monitoring is key to long-term success.

Outlook

Integrative strategies have significant potential to provide highly flexible, affordable solutions for individual growers' environmental and economic situation, but support is required during the transition phase towards the lower input system [3], where some experimentation with alternative crop varieties and management approaches may be necessary.

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6 VARIABLE RATE APPLICATION MANURE TASKMAPS

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KEYWORDS: precise fertilisation, slurry application, nutrient loss

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): Variable rate application manure taskmaps

Background

Variable rate application of manure on the field is an innovative technology that can considerably reduce nutrient losses & GHG emissions. This is done by both combining new data technologies & NPK sensors to optimise the application of manure, as well as by optimising the machinery used for application. This will lead to less emissions and nutrient losses.

Optimised variable rate application based upon NPK steered taskmaps

For the data aspect, farmers and contractors can use task maps based on N, P or K steering combined with an NPK sensor on the machines to optimise the spreading of the manure. Today the variable rate steering of manure is mostly done on cubes/ha and not on the real nutrient content of the applied manure (or at least not on the variable content). Today mostly one data point is taken that is used to optimise the variable rate application. Result maps are also freely available in Vervaet Connect and can be shared with several farm management information systems.

What would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented?

The main added value is to be found in the optimal use of the manure on the fields to be more cost efficient (avoiding extra application). Detailed maps are available to follow-up the yield afterwards.

How can the practitioner make use of the results?

The end-user can use this technology with Vervaet machinery if variable taskmaps are available before applying manure on the fields. Commercial tools or advisory services can be addressed to generate these variable rate application maps which can be uploaded to the machinery. User can use Vervaet Connect to see the maps.

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN NATIVE LANGUAGE): Taakkaarten voor mesttoediening met variabele dosering

Achtergrond

Het op variabele snelheid toedienen van mest op het veld is een innovatieve technologie die nutriëntenverliezen en broeikasgasemissies aanzienlijk kan verminderen. Dit gebeurt zowel door het combineren van nieuwe datatechnologieën en NPK-sensoren om de toediening van mest te optimaliseren, als door het optimaliseren van de machines die voor de toediening worden gebruikt. Dit leidt tot minder uitstoot en verlies van voedingsstoffen.

Geoptimaliseerde variabele toediening op basis van NPK-gestuurde taakkaarten

Voor het gegevensaspect kunnen boeren en loonwerkers taakkaarten gebruiken op basis van N, P of K sturing in combinatie met een NPK-sensor op de machines om het uitrijden van de mest te optimaliseren. Vandaag de dag wordt het sturen van de variabele hoeveelheid mest meestal gedaan op basis van blokjes/ha en niet op basis van werkelijke nutriëntengehalte van de uitgereden mest (of in ieder geval niet op basis van het variabele gehalte). Tegenwoordig wordt meestal één gegevenspunt genomen dat wordt gebruikt om de variabele toediening te optimaliseren.

Wat is de belangrijkste toegevoegde waarde/voordeel/mogelijkheid voor de eindgebruiker als de gegenereerde kennis wordt geïmplementeerd?

De belangrijkste toegevoegde waarde zit in het optimale gebruik van de mest op de velden om kostenefficiënter te zijn (voorkomen van extra toediening).

Hoe kan de praktijk de resultaten gebruiken?

De eindgebruiker kan deze technologie gebruiken met Vervaet machines als er variabele taakkaarten beschikbaar zijn voor het uitrijden van mest op het land. Er kan een beroep worden gedaan op commerciële tools of adviesdiensten om deze kaarten voor variabele toediening te genereren die naar de machines kunnen worden geüpload.

APPENDIX:

More info on NPK sensors can be found at:

<https://www.deere.co.uk/en/precision-agriculture/site-specific-farming/harvestlab-3000/>

<https://www.dinamicagenerale.com/en-ww/evonir.aspx>

More info on taskmaps can be found at:

<https://www.wur.nl/en/article/smart-manure-application-utilisation-a-practical-tool-for-issuing-advice-on-manure-application.htm>

7 USING VEGSYST-DSS TO PREPARE IRRIGATION AND N PLANS FOR FERTIGATED VEGETABLE CROPS GROWN IN GREENHOUSES

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KEYWORDS: decision support system, irrigation, nitrogen, vegetable crops, greenhouse

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): Using VegSyst-DSS to prepare irrigation and N plans for fertigated vegetable crops grown in greenhouses

Background

Tools are required to reduce the overapplication of water and fertiliser nitrogen (N) to vegetable crops in Mediterranean greenhouses.

The ECONUTRUI solution

The decision support system (DSS) VegSyst-DSS prepares site and crop specific plans for optimal management of N and irrigation for soil-grown vegetable crops in Mediterranean greenhouses, for tomato, pepper, cucumber, zucchini, melon, watermelon and eggplant.

Description of the suggested technology

The software has very few inputs and is simple to use for farmers and advisors. Input data for each crop are: climate (air temperature, solar radiation) from a long-term data base, and the dates of the crop. Greenhouse data is of soil, irrigation system, and most recent manure application. Calculations using long term average climate data provides detailed plans, prior to transplanting of N and irrigation applications for whole crop cycle. Output is daily amount of irrigation and N to apply, plus average N concentration to apply by fertigation over four-week periods. An English version can be freely downloaded: <http://www.ual.es/GruposInv/nitrogeno/index.shtml>.

Limitations

The plans for irrigation and N are approximate. Supplementary monitoring is recommended.

Outlook

The DSS is being continually improved. It will be a useful tool for preparing plans for N fertilisation required by new legislation.

Appendix

More information and manuals (in English and Spanish) on the practical use of the DSS are available at <http://www.ual.es/GruposInv/nitrogeno/index.shtml>. A divulgative article (in Spanish) is available at <https://www.interempresas.net/Horticola/Articulos/147844-Software-VegSyst-DSS-calcular-dosis-riego-necesidades-N-concentracion-N-fertirriego.html>.

Scientific descriptions and evaluations (in English) are available at <https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae9101128>, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2022.107973>, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-014-0427-3>

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ABSTRACT TITLE (NATIVE LANGUAGE): Uso de vegsyst-dss para preparar planes de riego y n para cultivos hortícolas en invernadero con fertirriego

Antecedentes

Se necesitan herramientas para reducir la sobre aplicación de agua y N a los cultivos hortícolas en los invernaderos mediterráneos.

La solución ECONUTRUI

El sistema de apoyo a la toma de decisiones (DSS) VegSyst-DSS prepara planes específicos para el lugar y el cultivo para una gestión óptima del N y el riego para tomate, pimiento, pepino, calabacín, melón, sandía y berenjena, cultivados en suelo en invernaderos mediterráneos.

Descripción de la tecnología propuesta

El software tiene muy pocas entradas y es fácil de usar para los agricultores y asesores. Los datos de entrada para cada cultivo son datos climáticos (temperatura del aire, radiación solar) de una base de datos a largo plazo, y las fechas del cultivo. Los datos de entrada para el invernadero son algunos detalles del suelo, el sistema de riego y la aplicación de estiércol más reciente. Los cálculos pueden realizarse a partir de datos climáticos medios a largo plazo, lo que permite preparar planes de aplicaciones de N y riego para la duración del cultivo realizados antes de plantar el cultivo. El resultado es la cantidad diaria de riego y N a aplicar, y la concentración media de N a aplicar por fertirrigación durante periodos de cuatro semanas. Puede descargarse gratuitamente una versión en inglés y español en <http://www.ual.es/GruposInv/nitrogeno/index.shtml>.

Limitaciones

Los planes de riego y N son aproximados. Se recomienda un seguimiento complementario.

Perspectivas

El DSS se mejora continuamente. Será una herramienta útil para preparar los planes de fertilización nitrogenada exigidos por la nueva legislación.

Anexo

Más información y manuales (en inglés y español) sobre el uso práctico del DSS en <http://www.ual.es/GruposInv/nitrogeno/index.shtml>. Un artículo divulgativo (en español) está disponible en <https://www.interempresas.net/Horticola/Articulos/147844-Software-VegSyst-DSS-calculardosis-riego-necesidades-N-concentracion-N-fertirriego.html>.

Las descripciones y evaluaciones científicas (en inglés) están disponibles en <https://doi.org/10.3390/horticulturae9101128>, <https://doi.org/10.1016/j.agwat.2022.107973>, <https://doi.org/10.1007/s00271-014-0427-3>

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8 SMART IRRIGATION MANAGEMENT TO OPTIMIZE THE NUTRIENT USE EFFICIENCY IN ORGANIC TOMATO CROPS

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KEYWORDS: organic agriculture, nutrient use efficiency (NUE), irrigation strategies

ABSTRACT TITLE: Smart irrigation management to optimize the nutrient use efficiency in organic tomato crops

Background

In organic farming, nitrogen (N) is a primary productivity constraint as this cropping system excludes the use of inorganic N fertilisers, while setting a maximum threshold of 170 kg N/ha annually for N application originating from animal manure (EU regulation 2018/848). It is therefore important to employ cultivation practices that maximise agronomic nutrient use efficiency of N. In conventional greenhouse tomato crops, most fertilizers are delivered through the drip irrigation system, thus ensuring that they are accessible by the root system [1]. However, in organic tomato farming, N is delivered through basal dressing, incorporating appropriate amounts of organic fertilisers into the soil bulk [2, 3]. However, this practice may result in N waste, as an appreciable quantity of fertilizers is incorporated in soil parts where no water is delivered through the drip irrigation system and thus no roots are developed.

The EcoNutri Solution

Smart irrigation strategies could be deployed to tackle this problem by using portable drippers as root navigators. Portable drippers that their point and distance alter along with the plant development could be employed to expand the root zone to a larger volume of soil and concomitantly utilise more N, thereby considerably increasing the nitrogen use efficiency.

Limitations

Application of this technology requires more effort by the grower and a more expensive irrigation system.

Outlook

This technique would not only benefit root growth, that is necessary for proper water and nutrient uptake and thus vigorous aboveground biomass development, but also will enhance crop nutrient use efficiency by optimizing utilization of the fertilizers applied through basal dressing.

ABSTRACT TITLE: Έξυπνη διαχείριση άρδευσης για μεγιστοποίηση της αξιοποίησης των θρεπτικών στοιχείων σε βιολογικές καλλιέργειες τομάτας

Υπόβαθρο

Στη βιολογική γεωργία, το άζωτο είναι ο σημαντικότερος περιοριστικός παράγοντας για υψηλές αποδόσεις λόγω της απαγόρευσης χρήσης ανόργανων λιπασμάτων N, επιβάλλοντας ως ανώτατο όριο παροχής αζώτου μέσω ζωικής κοπριάς τα 17 kg N/στρέμμα ετησίως (EU regulation 2018/848). Δεδομένων αυτών των περιορισμών, είναι υψίστης σημασίας η εφαρμογή καλλιεργητικών πρακτικών που αυξάνουν την αξιοποίηση του παρεχόμενου N από τις καλλιέργειες. Στη συμβατική καλλιέργεια τομάτας, τα λιπάσματα εφαρμόζονται συνήθως μέσω συστημάτων στάγδην άρδευσης, διασφαλίζοντας την παροχή όλων των θρεπτικών στοιχείων στη ριζόσφαιρα των φυτών [1]. Αντίθετα, στη βιολογική καλλιέργεια, τα θρεπτικά στοιχεία παρέχονται στην καλλιέργεια μέσω της βασικής λίπανσης, με ενσωμάτωση των λιπασμάτων εντός του εδάφους [2, 3]. Η πρακτική αυτή οδηγεί σε σπατάλη λιπάσματος, καθώς σημαντική ποσότητα αυτών ενσωματώνεται σε περιοχές του εδάφους που δεν αρδεύονται και άρα δεν αναπτύσσονται ρίζες.

Η λύση του EcoNutri

Έξυπνες στρατηγικές άρδευσης θα μπορούσαν να αποτελέσουν σημαντική λύση, χρησιμοποιώντας φορητούς σταλάκτες ως πλοηγούς ριζών. Σταλάκτες που το σημείο και η απόστασή τους μεταβάλλονται με την ανάπτυξη των φυτών δύναται να προωθήσουν την επιμήκυνση των ριζών σε μεγαλύτερο όγκο εδάφους και να τον αξιοποιήσουν για άντληση θρεπτικών στοιχείων.

Περιορισμοί

Η εφαρμογή αυτής της τεχνολογίας απαιτεί μεγαλύτερη προσπάθεια από τον καλλιεργητή και ένα πιο ακριβό σύστημα άρδευσης.

Προοπτική

Η τεχνική αυτή θα ενισχύσει την αποδοτικότητα της χρήσης των θρεπτικών στοιχείων από την καλλιέργεια, βελτιστοποιώντας τη χρήση των λιπασμάτων που ενσωματώθηκαν στον αγρό μέσω της βασικής λίπανσης.

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9 RECYCLING THE FERTIGATION EFFLUENTS IN CLOSED-LOOP SOILLESS CROPS USING ION SELECTIVE ELECTRODES AND THE DECISION SUPPORT SYSTEM NUTRISENSE

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KEYWORDS: hydroponics, precision agriculture, real-time sensing, automated nutrient management, nutrient recycling

ABSTRACT TITLE: Recycling the fertigation effluents in closed-loop soilless crops using ion selective electrodes and the decision support system NUTRISENSE

Background

Recycling of the drainage solution (DS) in closed-loop soilless culture systems (CLS) can reduce water and fertilizer losses by 30-50% and prevent pollution of water resources by nitrates [1]. An important challenge in CLS is to harmonize the supply with the uptake of nutrients. In CLS, this is essential to eliminate the need to discharge DS due to nutrient accumulation or depletion in the root zone. However, this is a challenge in CLS because the DS composition is variable and not predictable [2].

The ECONUTRI solution

ECONUTRI has developed a novel strategy based on the daily readjustment of the nutrient supply to levels maintaining the target macronutrient concentrations in the root zone of the crop using the decision support system (DSS) NUTRISENSE (<https://nutrisense.online>). Thus, if the raw water used to prepare nutrient solution does not contain NaCl at excessive concentrations (>2-3 mM), the discharge DS is eliminated. To daily recalculate the nutrient injection rates, NUTRISENSE is fed with the actual macronutrient concentrations in the DS which are measured daily using ion selective electrodes (ISEs). The fertilizer injection rates estimated by NUTRISENSE are automatically transmitted to the fertigation system and implemented in real time [3].

Limitations

To change the fertilizer injection rates daily, the fertigation system is equipped with eight individual fertilizer stock solutions plus one more injecting acid for the adjustment of pH in the outgoing nutrient solution.

Outlook

Daily monitoring of the DS composition using ISEs and readjustment of the nutrient addition using a suitable software such as NUTRISENSE not only optimises nutrient management but also facilitates the widespread adoption of CLS [4].

ABSTRACT TITLE: Αυτοματοποιημένη διαχείριση της θρέψης στα κλειστά υδροπονικά συστήματα με την χρήση ιοντοεκλεκτικών ηλεκτροδίων και του συστήματος υποστήριξης αποφάσεων NUTRISENSE

Το πρόβλημα

Η ανακύκλωση του διαλύματος απορροής (ΔΑ) σε κλειστά υδροπονικά συστήματα (ΚΥΣ) μειώνει τις απώλειες νερού και λιπασμάτων κατά 30-50% και αποτρέπει τη νιτρορύπανση [1]. Μια σημαντική πρόκληση στα ΚΥΣ είναι η εναρμόνιση της παροχής θρεπτικών στοιχείων με την πρόσληψή τους από τα φυτά, ώστε να αποτραπεί η ανάγκη απόρριψης ΔΑ λόγω συσσώρευσης ή έλλειψης θρεπτικών στοιχείων στη ζώνη της ρίζας. Ωστόσο, αυτός ο στόχος παρουσιάζει δυσκολίες επειδή η σύνθεση του ΔΑ είναι μεταβλητή και μη προβλέψιμη [2].

Η λύση του ECONUTRI

Το ECONUTRI έχει αναπτύξει μια καινοτόμα στρατηγική που βασίζεται στην καθημερινή αναπροσαρμογή της σύνθεσης του παρεχόμενου θρεπτικού διαλύματος (ΘΔ), ώστε να διατηρούνται οι επιθυμητές συγκεντρώσεις μακροθρεπτικών στο διάλυμα ριζοστρώματος, χρησιμοποιώντας το σύστημα υποστήριξης αποφάσεων NUTRISENSE (<https://nutrisense.online>). Με αυτή την τεχνολογία, αν το νερό που χρησιμοποιείται για παρασκευή ΘΔ είναι καλής ποιότητας, η ανάγκη απόρριψης ΔΑ εκλείπει. Για την καθημερινή αναπροσαρμογή της σύνθεσης του ΘΔ, το NUTRISENSE βασίζεται στις συγκεντρώσεις μακροθρεπτικών στο ΔΑ οι οποίες μετρούνται καθημερινά με ιοντοεκλεκτικά ηλεκτρόδια (ISE). Η νέα σύνθεση Θ.Δ. που υπολογίζει το NUTRISENSE διαβιβάζεται αυτόματα στην κεφαλή υδρολίπανσης και εφαρμόζεται σε πραγματικό χρόνο [3].

Περιορισμοί

Για να είναι δυνατή η καθημερινή τροποποίηση της συνταγής ΘΔ, η κεφαλή υδρολίπανσης πρέπει να είναι εξοπλισμένη με 8 δοχεία πυκνών διαλυμάτων λιπασμάτων συν ένα ακόμη με οξύ.

Προοπτικές

Ο καθημερινός έλεγχος της σύνθεσης του ΔΑ και η αναπροσαρμογή του παρεχόμενου ΘΔ με βάση ένα κατάλληλο λογισμικό όπως το NUTRISENSE βελτιστοποιεί την θρέψη των φυτών στα ΚΥΣ και συνεπώς ενθαρρύνει την περαιτέρω εξάπλωσή τους [4].

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10 CASCADE HYDROPONICS CAN INCREASE WATER AND NUTRIENTS USE EFFICIENCY OF GREENHOUSE PRODUCTION SYSTEMS

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KEYWORDS: soilless culture, nutrient recycling, salinity management

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): Cascade hydroponics can increase water and nutrients use efficiency of greenhouse production systems

Background

In soilless systems, reusing drainage solution (DS) enhances water (WUE) and nutrient use efficiency (NUE) while reducing environmental impact. However, fully closed hydroponic systems are impractical in regions with poor water quality due to the risk of salt accumulation and subsequent salinity stress.

The Econutri solution

The Cascade Hydroponic System (CHS) innovation deployed by Econutri addresses these challenges by employing a strategic drainage management approach [1]. This system uses the DS from a primary crop to fertigate one or more secondary crops that are tolerant to higher salinity levels. In this way, the water and nutrient needs of the secondary crop may be completely covered by the drainages of the primary crop.

Description of the suggested technology

The system maximizes the use of DS, therefore reducing production costs but also improving the quality characteristics of secondary crops. The CHS has demonstrated a more than 20% increase in WUE and NUE. Additionally, it has achieved significant reductions in nutrient leaching, with nitrogen and phosphorus leaching decreased by 75% and 86%, respectively.

Limitations

Converting an open hydroponic to a cascade system requires two tanks for storing the DS before and after disinfection. Optimal management involves adjusting pH, EC, and macronutrients ratios (adding macronutrients through ion selective sensors), as DS may have abnormal nutrients. Finally, the crop's DS may include phytotoxic root exudates or recirculated plant protection products.

Outlook

More research and pilot applications are required to validate the implementation of the system in practice.

ABSTRACT TITLE (NATIVE LANGUAGE): Τα υδροπονικά συστήματα επάλληλης χρήσης απορροών μπορούν να αυξήσουν την αποτελεσματικότητα χρήσης νερού και λιπασμάτων

Ιστορικό

Η ανακύκλωση των απορροών ενισχύει την αποδοτικότητα χρήσης νερού και λιπασμάτων, μειώνοντας τις περιβαλλοντικές επιπτώσεις. Ωστόσο, τα κλειστά συστήματα δεν είναι βιώσιμα σε περιοχές με χαμηλή ποιότητα νερού λόγω του κινδύνου συσσώρευσης αλάτων.

Η λύση του Econutri:

Το υδροπονικό σύστημα επάλληλης χρήσης απορροών (CHS) αντιμετωπίζει αυτές τις προκλήσεις μέσω μιας στρατηγική διαχείρισης απορροών [1]. Το CHS αξιοποιεί τις απορροές μιας κύριας καλλιέργειας (Κ.Κ.) για την λίπανση μίας ή περισσότερων δευτερευουσών καλλιεργειών (Δ.Κ.) ανθεκτικών σε υψηλά επίπεδα αλατότητας Έτσι, οι ανάγκες σε νερό και θρεπτικά στοιχεία της Δ.Κ. μπορεί να καλυφθούν πλήρως από τις απορροές της Κ.Κ.

Περιγραφή της προτεινόμενης τεχνολογίας

Το σύστημα μεγιστοποιεί τη χρήση των απορροών, μειώνοντας το κόστος παραγωγής και βελτιώνοντας τα ποιοτικά χαρακτηριστικά των Δ.Κ. Το CHS έχει δείξει αύξηση άνω του 20% στην αποδοτικότητα χρήσης νερού και θρεπτικών. Επιπλέον, έχει επιτύχει σημαντικές μειώσεις στη έκλυση θρεπτικών ουσιών, με το άζωτο και φώσφορο να μειώνονται κατά 75% και 86%.

Περιορισμοί

Το CHS απαιτεί δύο δεξαμενές αποθήκευσης της απορροής, πριν και μετά την απολύμανσή της. Η βέλτιστη διαχείριση απαιτεί διόρθωση του pH, της EC και των αναλογιών των στοιχείων (με προσθήκη λιπασμάτων μέσω ιοντοεκλεκτικών αισθητήρων) καθώς το διάλυμα απορροής μπορεί να μην έχει ισορροπημένες αναλογίες θρεπτικών. Τέλος, η απορροή μπορεί να περιλαμβάνει φυτοτοξικές εκκρίσεις ριζών ή ανακυκλωμένα προϊόντα φυτοπροστασίας.

Προοπτικές

Απαιτείται περαιτέρω έρευνα και πιλοτικές εφαρμογές για την επιβεβαίωση της αξιοπιστίας του συστήματος, ώστε να μπορεί να εφαρμοστεί στην πράξη.

Appendix: More Information on this innovative technology

For detailed information about the cascade hydroponic system and its benefits, readers can refer to several key sources. Karatsivou et al. (2023) provide a comprehensive analysis of drainage management strategies in soilless systems emphasizing the importance of nutrient and water reuse. Additionally, as part of the Econutri project, UTH has submitted an article to *Scientia Horticulturae*, currently under revision, titled "Cascade Hydroponics Enhance Water and Nutrients Use Efficiency in Greenhouses."

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11 THE USE OF UREASE INHIBITORS TO REDUCE AMMONIA AND GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS FROM DAIRY BARNs

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KEYWORDS: livestock housing, N excretion, urease inhibitor, NH₃ emissions

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): The use of urease inhibitors to reduce ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions from dairy barns

Background

The urease enzyme catalyses the hydrolysis of released urea through binding to its nickel containing active site and converts it to NH₃ and bicarbonate. Half time of the urease catalysed reaction is only 20 ms at 25°C leading to fast hydrolysis of urea in slurry.

The ECONUTRI solution

Is to inhibit the breakdown of urea to NH₃ and bicarbonate through the urease enzyme by using a urease inhibitor (UI). UI are chemical and biological compounds, which inhibit the binding of urea to the active site of the urease enzyme and thus stop the hydrolysis process of urea. For this purpose, it is suggested to apply an UI on the dairy barn floor at least once per day, ideally through an automatic application system (AAS). The AAS shall be configured as part of the cleaning robots so that it can apply a pre-defined concentration of UI on the floor during the cleaning process it. The use of UI on the barn floor has the potential to reduce NH₃ emissions up to ~50% [1]. The reduction in NH₃ emissions varies with the season with higher reductions during winter (65-68%) as compared to the summer season (40-53%).

Limitations

Currently, there are restrictions in the implementation of the UIs including the availability of AAS and their compatibility with the design of the barns and floor as well as legal restrictions on applying UIs in the barns.

Outlook

The application of UI has advanced, especially with automated methods, and the plans are to further evaluate the effectiveness of UI by using AAS which has the potential to be more effective in reducing emissions.

Appendix: It is an emerging technology in the livestock sector and only a few documents are available from where the readers can get detailed information about this technology. For example an interesting study

conducted by Bobrowski et al. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2021.01.011>) where they tested urease inhibitor in naturally ventilated dairy barns in Germany. An interesting review paper by Nugrahaeningtyas et al. (<https://doi.org/10.5187%2Fjast.2022.e5>) is also available which summarises the potential of this technology in livestock sector. For further detailed information readers can consult the thesis of Anna Barbara Bobrowski (https://macau.uni-kiel.de/receive/macau_mods_00000922?lang=en).

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN NATIVE LANGUAGE): Der Einsatz von Urease-inhibitoren zur Verringerung von ammoniak- und Treibhausgasemissionen aus Milchviehställen

Hintergrund

Das Enzym Urease katalysiert die Hydrolyse von Harnstoff durch Bindung an seine nickelhaltige aktive Stelle und wandelt ihn in NH₃ und Bikarbonat um. Die Halbwertszeit der durch Urease katalysierten Reaktion beträgt nur 20 ms bei 25°C, was zu einer schnellen Hydrolyse von Harnstoff führt.

Die ECONUTRI-Lösung

ist die Hemmung des Abbaus von Harnstoff zu NH₃ und Bikarbonat durch das Enzym Urease mit Hilfe eines Urease-Inhibitors (UI). UI sind chemische und biologische Verbindungen, die die Bindung von Harnstoff an die aktive Stelle des Urease-Enzyms hemmen und so den Hydrolyseprozess von Harnstoff stoppen. Zu diesem Zweck wird empfohlen, mindestens einmal täglich einen UI auf den Boden des Milchviehstalls aufzubringen, idealerweise über ein automatisches Ausbringungssystem (AAS). Das AAS muss als Teil der Reinigungsroboter so konfiguriert sein, dass es während des Reinigungsprozesses eine vordefinierte Konzentration von UI auf den Boden aufbringen kann. Der Einsatz von UI auf dem Stallboden hat das Potenzial, die NH₃-Emissionen um bis zu 50 % zu reduzieren (Bobrowski et al., 2021). Die Verringerung der NH₃-Emissionen variiert je nach Jahreszeit, wobei die Verringerung im Winter (65-68 %) höher ist als im Sommer (40-53 %).

Einschränkungen

Derzeit gibt es Einschränkungen bei der Anwendung von UI, darunter die Verfügbarkeit von AAS und ihre Kompatibilität mit der Konstruktion der Ställe und des Bodens sowie rechtliche Einschränkungen bei der Anwendung von UI in den Ställen.

Ausblick

Die Anwendung von UI hat sich weiterentwickelt, insbesondere mit automatisierten Methoden, und es ist geplant, die Wirksamkeit von UI durch den Einsatz von AAS weiter zu evaluieren und zu optimieren.

Anhang: Es handelt sich um eine aufstrebende Technologie im Tierhaltungssektor, und es sind nur wenige Dokumente verfügbar, aus denen die Leser detaillierte Informationen über diese Technologie erhalten können. Zum Beispiel eine interessante Studie von Bobrowski et al. (<https://doi.org/10.1016/j.biosystemseng.2021.01.011>), in der sie Ureaseinhibitoren in natürlich belüfteten Milchviehställen in Deutschland getestet haben. Eine interessante Übersichtsarbeit von Nugrahaeningtyas et al. (<https://doi.org/10.5187%2Fjast.2022.e5>) ist ebenfalls verfügbar, die das Potenzial dieser Technologie im Tierhaltungssektor zusammenfasst. Für weitere detaillierte Informationen können die Leser die Dissertation von Anna Barbara Bobrowski (https://macau.uni-kiel.de/receive/macau_mods_00000922?lang=en) konsultieren.

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12 REDUCING GHG AND NH₃ EMISSIONS FROM BARNs AND DURING STORAGE OF ORGANIC RESIDUES THROUGH BIOCHAR

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KEYWORDS: biochar, manure

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): Reducing GHG and NH₃ emissions from barns and during storage of organic residues through biochar

Background

Livestock production accounts for 10-15% of global greenhouse gas emissions. Significant amounts of gases, like methane (CH₄), nitrous oxide (N₂O) and carbon dioxide (CO₂) are emitted not only in barns but also during the external storage of manure coming from the livestock farms.

The ECONUTRI solution

The innovation of the work refers to the reduction of GHG and NH₃ emissions from livestock manure by using biochar [1]. The biochar application on top of the manure layer (5% w/w and 10% w/w) highlighted its potential importance for large scale field trials in due to the reduction of the emissions [2, 3].

Description of the suggested technology

The biochar is applied in external storages of livestock residues or inside the barn at a percentage higher than 3%.

Limitations

Optimization of the method and actions to convince producers of the potential benefits of biochar. Furthermore, the impact of various environmental conditions, such as local humidity and temperatures in different geographical areas should be examined to evaluate the efficiency of the biochar.

Outlook

As the reduction of GHG and NH₃ emissions is a target for climate change mitigation, this innovation based on the application of additives like biochar is valid. Although the proposed innovation is an easy and low investment approach, other cheaper and more effective additives or techniques appearing in the future may eventually replace the use of biochar to reduce GHG and NH₃ emissions.

ABSTRACT TITLE (NATIVE LANGUAGE): Μείωση των εκπομπών αερίων του θερμοκηπίου και NH₃ σε φάρμες και συγκεντρώσεις οργανικών υπολειμμάτων με την χρήση βιοεξανθρακώματος (Biochar)

Το πρόβλημα

Η ζωική παραγωγή ευθύνεται για το 10-15% των παγκόσμιων εκπομπών αερίων θερμοκηπίου. Σημαντικές ποσότητες αερίων, όπως το μεθάνιο (CH₄), το υποξείδιο του αζώτου (N₂O) και το διοξείδιο του άνθρακα (CO₂) εκπέμπονται όχι μόνο σε φάρμες, αλλά και κατά την εξωτερική αποθήκευση κοπριάς που προέρχεται από τις κτηνοτροφικές εκμεταλλεύσεις.

Η λύση που προτείνει το ECONUTRI

Η καινοτομία της εργασίας αναφέρεται στη μείωση των εκπομπών αερίων του θερμοκηπίου και NH₃ από την κοπριά των ζώων με την χρήση βιοεξανθρακώματος, το οποίο είναι ένα πλούσιο σε άνθρακα υπόλειμμα που προέρχεται από την πυρόλυση της βιομάζας [1]. Εάν η μείωση αυτών των αερίων αποδειχτεί σημαντική, θα μπορούσε να συμβάλει στον μετριασμό της κλιματικής αλλαγής [2, 3].

Περιγραφή προτεινόμενης τεχνολογίας.

Η προτεινόμενη μέθοδος είναι η εφαρμογή βιοεξανθρακώματος στους εξωτερικούς σωρούς κοπριάς των ζώων, καθώς και μέσα στη φάρμα. Αυτό μπορεί να επιτευχθεί είτε με την εφαρμογή μιας ορισμένης ποσότητας στην επιφάνεια της κοπριάς, είτε με την ανάμιξη του βιοεξανθρακώματος με την κοπριά πριν από την αποθήκευση.

Περιορισμοί

Απαιτείται βελτιστοποίηση της μεθόδου και περαιτέρω ενέργειες για να πειστούν οι παραγωγοί για τα πιθανά οφέλη του βιοεξανθρακώματος. Επιπλέον, θα πρέπει να εξεταστεί η επίδραση διαφόρων περιβαλλοντικών συνθηκών, όπως η τοπική υγρασία και οι θερμοκρασίες σε διαφορετικές γεωγραφικές περιοχές, προκειμένου να αξιολογηθεί η αποτελεσματικότητα του χρησιμοποιούμενου αυτού προσθέτου.

Προοπτικές

Εφόσον η μείωση των εκπομπών αερίων του θερμοκηπίου και NH₃ είναι ένας από τους στόχους για τον μετριασμό της κλιματικής αλλαγής, η καινοτομία, η οποία βασίζεται στην εφαρμογή προσθέτων, όπως το βιοεξανθράκωμα, θα παρουσιάζει ενδιαφέρον.

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13 REDUCTION OF GHG EMISSIONS IN VINEYARDS BY APPLYING ORGANIC FERTILIZATION PRACTICES

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KEYWORDS: organic farming, viticulture, GHG, legume

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): Reduction of GHG emissions in vineyards by applying organic fertilization practices

Background

Vineyards are usually located in soils which are characterized by low organic carbon content and a high risk of soil erosion. In viticulture, opportunities for mitigation of GHG emissions include reducing emissions related to energy production and transportation, minimizing N₂O emissions arising from inorganic and organic fertilisers, as global warming potential of N₂O is about 300 times higher than that of CO₂, and sequestering organic carbon in the soil [1].

The ECONUTRI solution

Viticulture, compared to other agricultural sectors, is less polluting [2]. The management of the soil in the vineyards, however, with the aim of preserving it, is of primary importance, not only for the yield and quality of the grapes, but also for the preservation of the ecosystem, which is endangered by climate change. Instead of conventional mowing and continuous chemical fertiliser inputs, ECONUTRI proposes alternative sustainable strategies giving a primary role to the preservation of biodiversity, the maintenance of soil fertility and the balance between vegetative and reproductive growth [3].

Description of the suggested technology

The following alternative treatments [4] are suggested for vineyards: i) cultivation of legumes with soil milling; ii) only grass cutting; iii) use of grounded canes; iv) cultivation with soil milling.

Limitations

Plant residues free of pathogens and transition to new cultivation practices are required.

Outlook

With the adoption of the technologies proposed by ECONUTRI, viticulture could significantly contribute to the global efforts to mitigate greenhouse gas emissions, while maintaining the productivity of vineyards and the quality of wine products.

ABSTRACT TITLE (NATIVE LANGUAGE): Μείωση των εκπομπών αερίων θερμοκηπίου στους αμπελώνες μέσω πρακτικών οργανικής λίπανσης

Υπόβαθρο

Οι αμπελώνες βρίσκονται συνήθως σε εδάφη με χαμηλή περιεκτικότητα σε οργανικό άνθρακα και υψηλό κίνδυνο διάβρωσης. Στην αμπελοκαλλιέργεια οι δυνατότητες περιορισμού των εκπομπών αερίων του θερμοκηπίου, περιλαμβάνουν τη μείωση των εκπομπών που οφείλονται στην παραγωγή ενέργειας και τις μεταφορές, την ελαχιστοποίηση των εκπομπών N₂O από ανόργανη και οργανική λίπανση, καθώς το N₂O έχει περίπου 300 φορές υψηλότερη επίπτωση στην υπερθέρμανση της γης σε σύγκριση με το CO₂, και τη δέσμευση οργανικού άνθρακα στο έδαφος [1].

The ECONUTRI solution

Η αμπελοκαλλιέργεια, σε σχέση με άλλους αγροτικούς τομείς είναι λιγότερο ρυπογόνος [2]. Η διαχείριση του αμπελοαγροτικού εδάφους, όμως είναι πρωταρχικής σημασίας, όχι μόνο για την απόδοση και την ποιότητα των σταφυλιών, αλλά και για τη διατήρηση της ισορροπίας του οικοσυστήματος που τίθεται σε κίνδυνο από την κλιματική αλλαγή. Σε σύγκριση με το συμβατικό όργωμα και τις συνεχείς εισροές, το ECONUTRI προτείνει εναλλακτικές τεχνικές με προτεραιότητα στη διαφύλαξη της βιοποικιλότητας, τη διατήρηση της γονιμότητας του εδάφους και την ισορροπία βλάστησης-καρποφορίας [3].

Περιγραφή των προτεινόμενων τεχνολογιών

Προτείνονται εναλλακτικά οι παρακάτω τεχνολογίες [4]: i) Καλλιέργεια ψυχανθών με αναμόχλευση εδάφους; ii) μόνο χορτοκοπή; iii) Χρήση θρυμματισμένων κληματίδων; iv) Κατεργασία με αναμόχλευση εδάφους.

Περιορισμοί

Απαιτούνται φυτικά υπολείμματα απαλλαγμένα παθογόνων και αλλαγές στις καλλιεργητικές πρακτικές.

Προοπτική

Με την υιοθέτηση αυτών τεχνικών η αμπελοκαλλιέργεια μπορεί να συμβάλει σημαντικά στις παγκόσμιες προσπάθειες περιορισμού των εκπομπών αερίων θερμοκηπίου, παράλληλα με τη διατήρηση της παραγωγικότητας και ποιότητας των αμπελοοινικών προϊόντων.

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14 REDUCTION OF GHG EMISSIONS WITH OPTIMISED MACHINERY

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ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): Reduction of GHG emissions with optimised machinery

Background

In this new innovative technology, we are focussing on the optimised application of manure on the field to reduce nutrient losses & GHG emissions. This is done by both combining new data technologies & NPK sensors to optimise the application of manure, as well as by optimising the machinery used for application. Both optimisations will lead to less emissions and nutrient losses. Farmers and contractors can use this technology to help their goals in terms of Green Deal challenges.

Optimised Vervaet manure machinery

The optimised machinery from Vervaet can be purchased when farmers or contractors are looking for new machinery. The adapted machinery will be optimised to reduce GHG emissions by reducing the contact of the manure with the open-air during field application & by using direct NPK sensor data of the NIR sensor (apply to correct dosing). These changes are all integrated into the new generation of machines.

What would be the main added value/benefit/opportunities to the end-user if the generated knowledge is implemented?

The main value of this optimised machinery is the reduction of GHG emissions & optimal use of the manure during application when using this innovation. This will help the end-user to comply with increased legislation in different countries.

How can the practitioner make use of the results?

This innovation is available when purchasing or using the compatible Vervaet machinery. Farmers can address the suitable contractor in their regions to use this new technology. The NIR sensor is an add-on feature.

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN NATIVE LANGUAGE): Reductie GHG-emissies met geoptimaliseerde mest machines

Achtergrond

In deze nieuwe innovatieve technologie richten we ons op de geoptimaliseerde toepassing van mest op het veld om nutriëntenverliezen en broeikasgasemissies te verminderen. Dit wordt gedaan door zowel nieuwe datatechnologieën en NPK-sensoren te combineren om het uitrijden van mest te optimaliseren, als door de machines die voor het uitrijden worden gebruikt te optimaliseren. Beide optimalisaties leiden tot minder uitstoot en verlies van voedingsstoffen. Boeren en loonwerkers kunnen deze technologie gebruiken om hun doelstellingen op het gebied van Green Deal te behalen.

Geoptimaliseerde Vervaet mestmachines

De geoptimaliseerde machines van Vervaet kunnen worden aangeschaft wanneer landbouwers of loonwerkers op zoek zijn naar nieuwe machines. De aangepaste machines worden geoptimaliseerd om de uitstoot van broeikasgassen te verminderen door het contact van de mest met de buitenlucht te verminderen en de juiste hoeveelheid mest toe te dienen gebaseerd op de nutriënt inhoud. Al deze veranderingen zijn geïntegreerd in de nieuwe generatie machines.

Wat is de belangrijkste toegevoegde waarde/voordeel/kans voor de eindgebruiker als de gegenereerde kennis wordt geïmplementeerd?

De belangrijkste waarde van deze geoptimaliseerde machines is de vermindering van de uitstoot van broeikasgassen & het optimaal gebruik van de mest bij gebruik van deze innovaties. Dit helpt de eindgebruiker om te voldoen aan de toegenomen wetgeving.

Hoe kan de gebruiker gebruik maken van de resultaten?

Deze innovatie is beschikbaar bij aankoop of gebruik van de compatibele Vervaet machines. Boeren kunnen de geschikte loonwerker in hun regio benaderen om deze nieuwe technologie te gebruiken. De NIR sensor is een optie.

APPENDIX

More info on NPK sensors can be found at:

<https://www.deere.co.uk/en/precision-agriculture/site-specific-farming/harvestlab-3000/>

<https://www.dinamicagenerale.com/en-ww/evonir.aspx>

More info on the Vervaet available machinery can be found on:

<https://www.vervaet.nl/en/products/manure-processing/>

15 THE USE OF AN EMISSION MONITORING SYSTEM TO REDUCE THE AMMONIA AND GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS FROM BARNES

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KEYWORDS: NH₃; ammonia; GHG; emissions; emission monitoring; sensors

ABSTRACT TITLE (IN ENGLISH): THE USE OF AN EMISSION MONITORING SYSTEM TO REDUCE THE AMMONIA AND GREENHOUSE GAS EMISSIONS FROM BARNES

Background

Ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions from livestock barns make up a large part of the agricultural emissions. They contribute to several global and local problems, such as global warming and acidification. Unlike factors that can visually be optimized through good farming practices such as animal productivity and welfare, the gas emissions of livestock barns are unknown to the farmer.

The ECONUTRI solution

The low-cost emission monitoring system OTICE gives livestock farmers insight in their barn climate and gas emissions. The system provides an online dashboard with real-time information that can be used to assess the effect of everyday farm management on the emitted gases [1]. This way, greenhouse gas and ammonia emissions can be reduced.

Description of the suggested technology

The OTICE system is built with open-source components that handle the data flow and visualisation. The data from wireless low-cost gas sensors can be transferred to the system to monitor the gas concentrations leaving the barn [2]. The system is scalable, meaning that sensors can be added or removed depending on the needs and configuration of the barn.

Limitations

The limitations of the system are the availability of reliable and durable low-cost sensors that can be used in barn environments and that provide options for real-time data transfer. Potential sensors are being tested and validated.

Outlook

The OTICE monitoring system can transform the barn emissions from an invisible cloud hanging over the farmer's head to a tangible optimization challenge [3]. Once the emissions of the barn and the effect of management decisions on them are made visible, the farmer has the handles to take control of the situation.

ABSTRACT TITLE (NATIVE LANGUAGE): HET GEBRUIK VAN EEN EMISSIE-MONITORINGSSYSTEEM OM DE AMMONIAK- EN BROEIKASGASEMISSIES VAN STALLEN TE VERLAGEN

Achtergrondinformatie

Ammoniak en broeikasgasemissies van stallen dragen bij aan verschillende lokale en globale problemen, zoals de opwarming van de aarde en verzuring. Anders dan bij het visueel optimaliseren van bijvoorbeeld productiviteitskenmerken en dierenwelzijn door het toepassen van goede landbouwpraktijken, zijn de emissies van een stal niet gekend door de veehouder.

De ECONUTRI oplossing

Het betaalbaar emissie-monitoringssysteem OTICE geeft veehouders inzicht in hun stalklimaat en gasemissies. Het systeem biedt een online dashboard met real-time informatie die gebruikt kan worden om het effect van het stalmanagement op de emissies te bepalen [1]. Zo kunnen ammoniak- en broeikasgasemissies verlaagd worden.

Beschrijving van de voorgestelde technologie

Het OTICE systeem is opgebouwd uit goedkope, draadloze sensoren en bestaat uit open source softwarecomponenten voor de datastroom en visualisatie, zodat de gasconcentraties van de uitgaande lucht kunnen opgevolgd worden [2]. Het systeem is uitbreidbaar waardoor sensoren toegevoegd of verwijderd kunnen worden afhankelijk van de noden en inrichting van de stal.

Beperkingen

De beperkingen van het systeem zijn de beschikbaarheid van betrouwbare, duurzame en goedkope sensoren die in een stalomgeving gebruikt kunnen worden en daarnaast real-time data-uitwisseling voorzien. Mogelijke sensoren worden getest en gevalideerd.

Vooruitzicht

Het OTICE emissie-monitoringssysteem kan emissies omtoveren van een donkere wolk die boven het hoofd van de veehouder hangt naar een tastbaar optimalisatieprobleem [3]. Zodra de emissies en de effecten van het stalmanagement hierop zichtbaar zijn heeft de veehouder handvaten ter beschikking om dit probleem verder aan te pakken.

Annex

A large limitation of the system is the availability of sensors that offer reliable gas concentration measurements and are durable in a barn environment. Several gas analyzers were validated for ammonia concentration measurements in barn environment (Zhuang et al., 2019; Zhuang et al., 2020). These systems, however, are expensive, hard to install and they need a lot of maintenance. Within the MilKey project, the search was started for wireless and low-cost sensors. The Van Mierlo sensors were tested (MilKey, 2024), but results were insufficient for reliable trend monitoring of ammonia nor for absolute values. Within Econutri, other options are being tested, like Dräger and VOCsSens sensors.

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